

Open Book Futures

Work Pack 7 Archiving and Digital Preservation: Policy Recommendations for National and International Policy Makers

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Table of contents

Table of contents	1
Author list	2
Contributor list	2
Document overview	3
Version history	3
Acronyms	3
Executive summary	5
Background Context	7
National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books	9
Context	9
Research	9
Policy Recommendations	10
Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses	13
Context	13
Research	13

Policy Recommendations	14
Copim Open Archiving Criteria	16
Context	16
Research	17
Policy Recommendations	17
Bibliography	19

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Acronyms

Acronyms are written out in full in the first instance, followed by their acronym in parentheses, and from there on in referred to by their acronym.

CC	Creative Commons
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COPIM	Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs
CILIP	Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DRM	Digital Rights Management
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
OA	Open Access
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OBF	Open Book Futures
MoSCoW	Must have, Should have, Could have, and Won't have

Executive summary

This report summarises the policy recommendations that have originated from the research and consultancy conducted as part of the Open Book Futures project, produced by the Archiving and Digital Preservation work package.

Following the background context of why these recommendations are needed and of their overarching philosophy, this report contains three policy briefings in the areas of: National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books; Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses; and the Copim Open Archiving Criteria.

The recommendations are:

National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books

- Legal deposit open access monographs should remain openly available under their original licence
- The open access status of a legal deposit open access monograph/associated deposited item should be clearly recorded in the associated metadata and catalogue records
- Open access licencing relating to the usage conditions of open access monographs, such as Creative Commons licences, should be documented and clearly displayed in cataloguing information
- Electronic legal deposit legislation should be passed for all national libraries by their correlating government
- All National Libraries should have a mechanism for the open display and download of approved content associated with open access monographs and this should link to other records for the same work within the National Library systems and catalogue

Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses

- Where e-Theses are university mandated and where possible – excluding those that have been embargoed, have copyright considerations or similar – e-Theses should be open access and openly available and digitally preserved
- There should be UK wide consistency and an agreement on the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses and their associated digital materials, and on the approach for

archiving and preserving digital materials and creative outputs that form the main body of the doctoral submission

- Responsibilities should be clarified across the different aspects of the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses within and across universities, including for staff and student training and ownership over the associated systems
- Doctoral training regarding data management and digitally preserving e-Theses should be mandated to be made available to both doctoral researchers and PhD supervisors from the point at which it is needed; and universities should utilise openly shared training materials, as well as making their own openly available
- As part of university training around scholarly communication and publishing, cognate to digital preservation, students and staff should be made aware of the need for long-term access and how this relates to issues such as embargoes, copyright and so on

Copim Open Archiving Criteria

- Open Access content should remain openly available
- Open Access book metadata should be openly available
- Archiving and preservation processes (for both content and metadata) should be openly verifiable
- The practices followed in operations as a digital archive should be evidenced and documented
- Risk registers for open archiving solutions should encompass risks outside of just the technical and include political risk, geographical risk and legislative risk

Although this report is comprehensive and interrelated in its recommendations for the archiving and digital preservation of open access books, the individual recommendations for ‘National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books’, ‘Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses’, and the ‘Copim Open Archiving Principles’ have been included as separate briefings in the appendices of this report. These separate briefings, as well as this report, should be openly shared with all the relevant listed stakeholders across national and international policy in digital preservation for use in their advocacy, and are intended for use in workshops, conferences, and policy focussed events. We also intend for these recommendations to be built upon by those making policy themselves, as well as by researchers and practitioners working in this area.

Background Context

Open Book Futures is a Research England and Arcadia funded project helping to transform scholar-led open access publishing. Publishing a work is only one step in a work's lifecycle. Once published, it needs to be found, used and re-used. The use and re-use could be many years after the publication date. As such, these works need to be preserved for future readers and scholars. Archiving and Preservation was an integral part of the project. The Archiving and Preservation Work Package on the Open Book Futures project has investigated current practice in this space with work focussed on:

- The role of National Libraries (particularly through the lens of Legal Deposit);
- The role of repositories (both institutional and generalist);
- The challenges of Link Rot;
- How to preserve PhD theses;
- The differences of archiving open access works as compared to traditional; subscription works.

The recommendations in this report are direct results of the research within this project and the previous COPIM project. The initial findings from COPIM can be found in our 2022 scoping report¹.

The over-arching assumption we have taken in framing these recommendations (and the related work throughout the project) is that open access works should remain open access (unless retracted). One of the many benefits of open access is the increased visibility the published work receives. However, much of the work amongst libraries and policy makers (and most of this on short form publications such as journal articles rather than books and monographs) has been on the requirements at the point of publication (e.g. licences, allowable embargo periods, funding for open access). Less thought has been given to the longevity of those works, especially when it comes to books and monographs. Existing preservation solutions in the scholarly world (such as Portico and CLOCKSS) are based on the principle of a "Dark Archive" where a preserved work is only made available once it is "Triggered" i.e. a publisher ceases to operate and their web content is no longer accessible. These services offer invaluable preservation processes at scale, but we argue in Copim's Open Archiving Criteria (Cole, Gatti, Higman, Stokes, Steiner, & Turpin 2026) that we need to evolve our thinking in what preservation means for an increasingly open access world (at least for scholarly work).

The coverage of these recommendations is deliberately broad because preservation covers a wide range of stakeholders.

¹ Barnes, M., Bell, E., Cole, G., Fry, J., Gatti, R., and Stone G., "WP7 scoping report on archiving and preserving OA monographs" <https://hdl.handle.net/2134/20222166>

Preservation is not always considered by funders, libraries, universities, governments etc. when considering open access policies. The recommendations are especially important now as scholarly communications generally face a financial sustainability crisis. In the UK, several universities have been forced to withdraw from agreements with publishers due to budgetary pressures (Barr 2025). At a time when budgets are being reduced and value for money is being scrutinised, the longevity of what is funded is critical. Preservation is essential for this longevity and, as such, these recommendations are part of that wider picture.

Other projects and organisations are also investigating and advocating for preservation to scholarly outputs. The Embedding Preservability Project builds on the Enhancing Services to Preserve new forms of Scholarship project and its 68 recommendations². In addition, the Digital Preservation Coalition publish a Global Bit List of Endangered Materials³ every 2 years. This highlights a range of research outputs as being Critically Endangered through to Vulnerable. These examples show that knowledge is at risk of being lost and highlight why preservation is critical to mitigating this loss.

As noted above, the over-arching recommendation from this project is that the open access status of a book should be preserved. This is both in practical terms (i.e. the open access status of a work should be captured and included in metadata associated with the work) but also as a general principle that once open access, a work should remain open access (as should be the case if it is published with, for example, a creative commons licence). For example, UK Legal Deposit legislation effectively “closes” a deposited open access book as all works are treated as if they are subscription works so are only available through dedicated terminals at legal deposit libraries.

Another recommendation that spans the various areas covered in this report is that archiving and digital preservation processes and practices themselves should be openly available and shared. This recommendation engages with both the underlying principles of open access publishing but is also in the interest of ensuring sustainable actions are taken in facing the challenges in the archiving and digital preservation of open access books.

² Embedding Preservability – Project led by NYU Libraries https://wp.nyu.edu/embedding_preservability/

³ The Global ‘Bit List’ of Endangered Digital Materials <https://bit-list.dpconline.org/>

National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books

Context

One of the key goals of the Archiving and Digital Preservation work package on the Open Book Futures project was to develop an international network of national libraries. This has been in recognition of the role that national libraries play in the archiving and digital preservation of open access books through the process of legal deposit. Legal deposit is a legal requirement that mandates individuals or organizations to submit copies of their publications to a designated repository, typically a national library. In the case of open access books, which by their nature are published with a digital edition, electronic legal deposit is imperative. Electronic legal deposit, since its beginnings in the early 21st century, has been implemented in a large proportion of national libraries and has been legislated in many of those same national library contexts. Electronic legal deposit is strongly correlated with digital preservation practices at national libraries. These practices are incredibly important not only in so far as they are able to maintain the open access status of open access books, but also as a means of preserving these publications for access by future users and readers.

To better understand current practices and workflows for the digital preservation of open access monographs in national libraries, and how these are impacted by the policy landscapes within which the national libraries operate, we held a series of process mapping workshops with selected national libraries participating in the National Libraries Network and additional national libraries.

These recommendations are intended for national libraries themselves, when addressing institutional policies and procedures, as well as for legislators in their national contexts. They also involve incidental recommendations for publishers preparing and depositing open access monographs.

Research

The process mapping workshops were intended to document the digital preservation lifecycle of an open access monograph through legal deposit workflows at 5 different national libraries. From these workshops we created 5 distinct case studies and 5 process maps documenting the phases of a lifecycle of an open access monograph being deposited to a national library. The corresponding phases were: 'identify'; 'acquisition'; 'pre-ingest'; 'ingest'; 'repository management'; 'digital preservation'; and 'access'. The libraries who took part in these workshops, from which

case studies and process maps have been produced, were the British Library, Library and Archives Canada, Qatar National Library, the National Library of Scotland and the National Library of the Czech Republic.

From these workshops we were able to determine areas of digital preservation of legal deposit workflows that could be changed to benefit open access monographs, as well as opportunities for a network of national libraries to share practice relating to the digital preservation of open access monographs. Furthermore, we also identified areas of policy that need to be addressed in the digital preservation of open access monographs by national libraries. The full report (Cole, Fry, Maynard & Turpin 2026) of this research can be accessed here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19912140>.

Policy Recommendations

As part of the work package Archiving and Digital Preservation on the Open Book Futures project, policy recommendations for national and international policy makers have been developed in the areas of National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books, Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses, and the Copim Open Archiving Criteria. These recommendations have been documented by the project in a Policy Recommendations report and are available as separate briefings. Below are the policy recommendations, based on the findings of this report. These recommendations are intended for National Libraries themselves, when addressing institutional policies and procedures, as well as for legislators in their national contexts. They also involve incidental recommendations for publishers preparing and depositing OA monographs.

1. Legal deposit open access monographs should remain openly available under their original licence

For open access content to be openly available the original published content (files) should be freely available to view and download by any reader with access to the internet through the National Library's catalogue. This recommendation is intended for National Libraries.

2. The open access status of a legal deposit open access monograph/associated deposited item should be clearly recorded in the associated metadata and catalogue records

This recommendation relates to findings in the research that in some cases when an open access monograph was deposited with a National Library the open access status was either not recorded in the associated metadata, or there was no clear field for this information to be provided to National Libraries. Clear and openly accessible information of the open access status of a monograph is not only important in the immediate deposit and availability of open access

monographs, but also incredibly important in the long-term preservation of this status both for future generations and if the open access monograph is reproduced and made available in other contexts. This recommendation is intended directly for National Libraries but should also be reflected in the information provided to publishers about how to complete the metadata field recommended above. We recommend National Libraries work with metadata standards organisations to ensure a consistency of approach.

3. Open access licencing relating to the usage conditions of open access monographs, such as Creative Commons licences, should be documented and clearly displayed in cataloguing information

This recommendation relates to the findings in the research that licences such as Creative Commons licences were not always clearly displayed in the cataloguing information of an open access monograph and that the onus was on the user to find this information within the publication itself or from the publisher. However clearly displayed licencing is important when considering not only the preservation of the open access status of an open access monograph, but also in archiving how these usage conditions may have changed or been altered over time. Again, we recommend National Libraries work with metadata standards organisations to ensure a consistency of approach.

4. Electronic legal deposit legislation should be passed for all National Libraries by their correlating government

This recommendation relates to the finding in one case that electronic legal deposit legislation had not been passed in the National Library's national context. Electronic legal deposit is incredibly important for open access monographs not only because by their nature open access publications will include a digital edition, but also because electronic deposit is what allows for these digital editions to be available to openly view and use online. This recommendation is intended for international governments and legislators.

5. All National Libraries should have a mechanism for the open display and download of approved content associated with open access monographs and this should link to other records for the same work within the National Library systems and catalogue

This recommendation is related to Copim's Open Archiving principles, which were developed by the work package on Archiving and Digital Preservation (Cole, Gatti, Higman, Stokes, Steiner, & Turpin 2026). Specifically, it is related to the principle that digital preservation platforms should be adopted to enable the open display and download of content. It also relates to the principle that there should be an openly available audit trail for each individual monograph, and that this is all provided in one place. This relates to the overarching philosophy of Open Book Future's policy recommendations that digital preservation practice should be more transparent. This

recommendation is intended for the National Libraries themselves, whilst recognising that each individual context will have its own challenges. However, this recommendation is also intended to aid the sharing of practice with other National Libraries, which was found in the research to be a way of furthering digital preservation practice.

Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses

Context

An area of focus for the Archiving and Digital Preservation work package on the Open Book Futures project has been the archiving and digital preservation of PhD Theses. Due to various reasons (perhaps the most important being that, during the COVID-19 pandemic many universities were forced into a rapid decision to require digital only submission of theses) there has been a recent increase in the proliferation of e-Theses. An e-Thesis is a digital version of a graduate student's research project. Unlike their printed counterparts, e-Theses are stored and shared electronically, offering enhanced accessibility, multimedia integration, and easy searchability. As a digital edition of the PhD Thesis, a large proportion of e-Theses are shared under open access agreements, meaning they increasingly represent a scholar's first experience of publishing open access. Furthermore, the open access deposit and long-term preservation of an e-Thesis raises fundamental considerations related to capturing important scholarly knowledge.

A key reason for placing a focus on e-Theses is that they have been declared 'vulnerable' in the Digital Preservation Coalition's 'Bit List' of digitally endangered species (2025 DPC BitList). Despite this vulnerable status, Currently, there is no recourse to universal good practice guidance regarding the archiving and preservation of e-Theses, with guidance varying across institutions.

To identify the main issues and challenges associated with archiving and preserving PhD Theses from the perspective of key stakeholders, Open Book Futures conducted research as a collaboration between researchers at Loughborough University and the Digital Preservation Coalition. This research investigated how, in the view of university library repository staff, doctoral college staff and registry staff, some of the above issues are addressed in current policy and procedures. A secondary question was when and how doctoral researchers receive information and guidance about these issues and considerations, and their understanding and views on the importance and relevance of digital preservation in relation to their thesis.

These recommendations are intended for both policy makers within individual universities and for those operating policy and defining practice on a university-wide basis in the UK.

Research

The research conducted by the researchers at Loughborough University and the Digital Preservation Coalition involved a survey measuring awareness of digital preservation and open access considerations distributed to PhD students and doctoral researchers in the UK, as well as 5 interviews with staff at university repositories across the UK. Supplementary to this research, a

staff survey was also distributed, and a focus group was held with doctoral researchers. The findings from this research identified challenges in the archiving and preservation of PhD Theses in the areas of: student and staff perceptions of PhD Theses/e-Theses; policies and responsibilities; technical practices; and skills and training. The full report (Cole, Fry, Maynard & Turpin 2026) of this research can be accessed here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19921160>

Policy Recommendations

1. Where e-Theses are university mandated and where possible - excluding those that have been embargoed, have copyright considerations or similar - e-Theses should be open access and openly available and digitally preserved

For e-Theses to be open access they should be openly available with all the associated files being freely available to view and download by any reader with access to the internet through a university repository or other relevant repository (e.g. through the British Library's EthOS platform). This recommendation is intended for university policy makers and university repositories.

2. There should be UK wide consistency and an agreement on the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses and their associated digital materials, and the approach for archiving and preserving digital materials and creative outputs that form the main body of the doctoral submission

This recommendation relates to findings in the research that there is currently no recourse to universal good practice guidance regarding the archiving and preservation of e-Theses, with guidance varying across institutions. It also relates to the findings around lack of awareness and knowledge in university staff and students around digitally complex PhD outputs and non-traditional Theses. This recommendation is intended for policymakers operating policy for UK universities, as well as national organisations in a position to agree best practice in these areas.

3. Responsibilities should be clarified across the different aspects of the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses within and across universities, including for staff and student training and ownership over the associated systems

This recommendation relates to findings in the research about disagreement and confusion around the responsibility for initially ensuring e-Theses are created in the correct format to be preserved in the long-term and whether this responsibility lies with students, supervisors, repository staff or other individuals within the organization. Furthermore, it was found that it is not clear who bears the responsibility for training and learning around digital preservation and for the long-term stewardship of e-Theses to ensure their continuing access and use. This recommendation is intended mostly for policy makers in universities; however, it does also relate

to the previous recommendation in that these responsibilities should form part of a UK-wide agreement on the approach for archiving and digitally preserving PhD Theses.

4. Doctoral training regarding data management and digitally preserving e-Theses should be mandated to be made available to both doctoral researchers and PhD supervisors from the point at which it is needed; and universities should utilise openly shared training materials, as well as making their own openly available

This recommendation relates to the findings around challenges faced in skills and training relating to digital preservation in universities, and to the conclusion that training is needed much earlier in the PhD process, as opposed to information being focussed solely on PhD submission. It also relates to the Digital Preservation Coalition open educational resources created as part of Open Book Futures, and in recognition of the importance of sharing practice across institutions. This recommendation is intended for university policy makers as well as for individuals and teams within universities responsible for providing information about and access to training.

5. As part of university training around scholarly communication and publishing, cognate to digital preservation, students and staff should be made aware of the need for long-term access and how this relates to issues such as embargoes, copyright and so on

This recommendation relates to findings emanating from the research around the perception and awareness of open access publications and digital preservation, and how the perceptions of staff such as PhD supervisors have an impact on the perception of students and therefore the actions they take or do not take in digitally preserving their PhD Thesis. It also relates to findings around misunderstanding specifically on issues such as embargoes and copyright leading to PhD Theses in some cases being unnecessarily closed access. This recommendation is intended for university policy makers, particularly those involved in university training, not just for PhD students and doctoral researchers, but also for academic training more generally.

Copim Open Archiving Criteria

Context

As part of the work of Open Book Futures on the Archiving and Digital Preservation work package, a criterion for open archiving have been developed. These principles are based on the project philosophy that open access books should remain open access and openly available throughout the digital preservation lifecycle. Open archiving more specifically, builds on the principles of openly shared practices and procedures and the idea that trust and transparency can be built into the process.

A key part of these principles relies on anyone being able to check the audit trail and therefore knowing what they are reading is what they think it is. This audit trail and the openly shared practices and procedures should enable other organisations to more easily take over the preservation, making sure that the digital preservation of open access books is continuous, sustainable beyond the initial digital preservation system and resilient to any political or social threats to their status as open access. These principles also are instrumental in allowing funders, publishers and authors to recommend what they from the digital preservation of open access books, as opposed to this being led by specific solutions. If funders recommend solutions, this should be from a position of knowledge rather than solely the known solutions. Furthermore, information needs to be given by providers so funders can assess the risks associated with any given solution.

These principles and the below recommendations were developed over the course of the project, coming from challenges faced when working with repositories to try and form a network, as well as conversations held with global digital preservation experts. Through this work and theses conversations, we are clear that this is one model and others exist which serve different purposes, these principles however are imperative for looking at what might be possible and what would be beneficial in the world of open access books. The Copim Open Archiving Criteria (Cole, Gatti, Higman, Stokes, Steiner, & Turpin 2026)., which also includes specific recommendations for practice, can be read in full here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882469>.

These recommendations are intended for all those involved in providing open archiving solutions, such as repositories and digital preservation solutions as well as wider stakeholders such as research funders and publishers.

Research

The Copim Open Archiving Criteria are a result of the work that Open Book Futures has conducted with repositories with the aim of creating an open archiving network. Through this work however it was found that what was needed was an in-depth consideration of the work of repositories, rather than seeking a breadth of repositories to be involved in this network. The challenges facing repositories that were identified in this work were associated with policies; staffing; and the sheer number of software types and versions of software.

Further to this work with repositories the work package on Archiving and Digital Preservation on the project also held an internal MoSCoW workshop to develop the principles in the first instance, based on a 'Must have, Should have, Could have, and Won't have' framework for open archiving solutions. Following this workshop the Digital Preservation Coalition facilitated a workshop with international digital preservation experts, which allowed the work package to modify the principles and their thinking based on this feedback. Following these workshops the criteria has been presented at several conferences including iPres and the CILIP Metadata Conference.

Policy Recommendations

1. Open Access content should remain openly available

This recommendation relates to both the availability of the published monograph and more widely to the availability of archival information about the monograph i.e. metadata, which is addressed in further recommendations. For open access content to be openly available the original published content (files) should be freely available to download by any reader with access to the internet, Digital Rights Management (DRM) free and under the same licence as the work itself, subject to any third-party copyright. Additionally, it should be possible for there to be bulk downloads of content to allow independent third party 'rescue' of content in case of archive failure and a permanent URL should be available to access the work (this means that the archived version URL can be included within the metadata and Digital Object Identifier (DOI) record of the work). This recommendation is intended for anyone actively archiving and digitally preserving open access content and those involved in determining open access requirements e.g funders.

2. Open Access book metadata should be openly available

In addition to the availability of the published monograph, book metadata should also be openly available and should always include the licence and usage rights. Metadata should be archived using a CC-0 licence, should be systematically associated with the book and should be available for all readers to download alongside the work itself. Furthermore, metadata should be versioned alongside any changed versions of the publication, ensuring that open metadata is linked to open

content. This recommendation is intended for anyone actively archiving and digitally preserving open access content, anyone creating open access metadata and those involved in determining metadata standards.

3. Archiving and preservation processes (for both content and metadata) should be openly verifiable

As referenced in the first and second recommendations, that open access content and open access metadata should be openly available, so too should archivable information about the content. This archivable information should include published checksums to allow verification of content integrity, transparent version control, transparent processes for verifying content and transparent preservation processes (if undertaken). This is so that all users can see the archive content and compare their version against it, ensuring that a record of versions is kept.

4. The practices followed in operations as a digital archive should be evidenced and documented

As well as recommending that archives should be open about their processes and standards, it is also recommended that these processes and standards are documented for users to access. These practices and standards should include sustainability and strategies for ensuring long-term provision of the archiving solution. The standards documented may include ISO standards, The Keeper's Registry standards or the OAIS model for digital preservation. Transparency around practices and standards empowers the wider community to undertake preservation, particularly in the wider political contexts where multiple solutions are needed to mitigate risk.

5. Risk registers for open archiving solutions should encompass risks outside of just the technical and include political risk, geographical risk and legislative risk

This recommendation is further to the above recommendations which engage with the need for open archiving practices being due to risk presented by political and geographical forces to openly accessible archived research and content. Regarding open archival practice this means that there should be multiple geographically redundant copies of open access books. As it is unlikely a single solution will ensure independence from private and government-controlled entities, this both needs to be reflected in archive risk registers, whilst also providing the wider digital preservation community with the knowledge and information needed to provide multiple solutions. This recommendation itself is for archives, ensuring that they are clear what legislation they are responsible to and what their technical infrastructure is built on, so users can decide which solutions to take from a position of transparency.

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